

International Water Conflicts in Central Asia Can Be Resolved Peacefully

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Abstract

How can countries peacefully share transboundary freshwater resources when climate change jeopardises water supplies while the demand for water keeps growing? This contribution focuses on international water disputes in Central Asia to illustrate this combined challenge. It draws from historical lessons in water management to provide insights into how Central Asian countries can navigate tensions over the most recent challenge in this domain, which pertains to the Qosh Tepa Canal in Afghanistan and has a strong impact on the Amu Darya.

Background

Climate change profoundly impacts environmental systems and the human populations depending on them.¹ Among these systems, freshwater resources are fundamental, as they sustain not only critical ecosystems—such as forests, wetlands, and grasslands—but also human societies. Scholars and policymakers increasingly note how climate-driven changes in precipitation and temperature patterns may lead to water scarcity, heightening risks of conflict within and between countries.

However, while the destabilizing potential of climate change is profound, the relationship between climate change, water scarcity, and conflict is complex and must be approached with nuanced analysis. This complexity arises from two interconnected pressures on freshwater resources. First, on the supply side, climate change directly affects the quantity and reliability of renewable water resources. Second, on the demand side, demographic and economic developments shape how much water societies withdraw and how effectively they manage supply-demand gaps. Historical analysis demonstrates that, despite tensions, international water disputes have predominantly been resolved through diplomatic and peaceful means.

Here we focus on Central Asia—a region historically shaped by intricate transboundary water management—to explore the potential for peaceful conflict resolution amid rising pressures from climate change and human water demands. The hydrological backbone of southern semi-arid Central Asia consists of two major river basins, the Syr Darya and the Amu Darya, which are part of the larger Aral Sea Basin (Figure 1).

We revisit empirical evidence regarding international water disputes globally to understand the likelihood of peaceful resolution in similar cases. We then provide the necessary context on the distinct hydrological and socio-economic conditions of Central Asia. This is followed by insights into the specific contemporary challenge posed by Afghanistan's Qosh Tepa Canal, which is expected to significantly affect the Amu Darya basin's water balance. All this allows us to assess whether historical patterns of peaceful conflict resolution can be expected to hold in the face of intensified pressures associated with climate change and the construction of the Qosh Tepa Canal.

Conflict and cooperation over water resources, globally and in Central Asia

To contextualize the situation in Central Asia, we first revisit the global landscape of international water conflict. Existing research shows that, historically, water management challenges around the world are overwhelmingly resolved through diplomacy and cooperation rather than violent means. Researchers have compiled a wealth of data on water-related events within and between countries, spanning many decades. The best available data is from the Water Conflict Management and Transformation program, the WARICC dataset,² and Kåresdotter et al.³ This research uses vast digitalized news-media archives that include reports from sources worldwide that are translated into English. These reports are systematically scanned for water-related events, and the news on these events is then characterized and coded according to how cooperative or conflictive the respective event was.

Figure 1: Overview of the Aral Sea Basin. The two main rivers, i.e., the Amu Darya and the Syr Darya, are shown in blue color. The rivers emerge from the high mountain regions and flow downstream towards the former Aral Sea (shown in the northwest corner of the map). In average years, most, if not all, water is consumed downstream, mainly for irrigation. As a result, the rivers no longer reach the Aral Sea. Red arrows show bulk water withdrawals. The width of the arrows/lines is proportional to the average flow. The black rectangle indicates the downstream region of Amu Darya, a future water scarcity hotspot. Source: Zoi Environment Network, 2018.

The main findings from this research are that events focused on solving water-related problems (cooperative events) are far more common than conflict events, although the proportion of conflictive events seems to have increased to some extent in recent years⁴. Moreover, hardly any of the conflict events observed involve violence on a larger scale, let alone full-fledged “water wars.”⁵ Even in upstream-downstream river settings, where the upstream country commonly has the incentive to abuse its geographic advantage and maximize its benefits from using the river at the expense of downstream countries, we do not observe more conflict than cooperation events.⁶ Most conflict results from large water infrastructure projects that alter the river flow and water availability downstream. Even in such cases, however, conflicts remain verbal and do not end in violence. In other words, international water wars are thus far a myth rather than a reality.

Will this trend continue under extreme climate change scenarios, where changes in precipitation and snow- and ice-melt dynamics could trigger more conflict over a shrinking water supply between countries and within nations? Either directly, or indirectly as a result of countries’ climate change adaptation strategies increasingly relying on the construction of ever more water storage reservoirs and water transfer infrastructure. The absence of water wars in the past does not guarantee that militarized water conflict in the future is impossible.

We adopt two approaches to assessing the likelihood of conflict in Central Asia over its two major water systems, the Syr Darya and Amu Darya. First, we examine water systems in arid and semi-arid areas of the world that have experienced extended periods of low precipitation and drought from an empirical/historical perspective. Then, we look at recent results from computational climate and hydrological models to explore what the future might bring. This, in turn, helps in making sense of the most recent international water challenge in Central Asia, which concerns the Qosh Tepa Canal in Afghanistan.

Could further climate change and increased water abstraction tip the balance?

The entirety of the Syr Darya and 70% of the Amu Darya were historically located in the Soviet Union, which took a unified, top-down management approach to all its water resources. This system collapsed with the end of the Soviet Union, thus fragmenting control of these rivers into a stark upstream-downstream hydro-political geography. Upstream countries, where runoff is generated, inherited large Soviet-era water reservoirs and have continued to build additional ones, granting them control of headwaters. The downstream countries remain highly dependent on this water, primarily for irrigated agriculture.

In the case of the Amu Darya, the Soviet-era water-sharing agreement was reinstated after the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the four riparian countries of Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan adhere to a water-sharing system monitored by the Interstate Commission for Water Coordination (ICWC).⁷ The ICWC divides the river's flow among the four countries yearly, depending on variable expected supply levels. It oversees water distribution, ensuring it meets the needs of upstream and downstream users. This continuity was facilitated by the limited to absent capacity of Afghanistan to build new water infrastructure and act as a significant player in regional water management at the time, primarily due to decades of armed conflict and the socio-economic decline of the country as a whole. With fewer competing demands and a stable allocation framework inherited from the Soviet period, the Amu Darya experienced rather little conflict with its riparian countries becoming independent states.

The existing international water-sharing framework for the Amu Darya continues to largely succeed in maintaining cooperation among the riparian countries, particularly during the non-growing season from October to March, when water demands are lower. However, during the critical growing season from April to September, water demand peaks, and the system faces more significant challenges, especially during dry years, such as the ongoing multi-year drought. Under these conditions, the downstream nations of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are particularly vulnerable, grappling with aging irrigation and drainage systems and significant losses due to canal leakage.

The Syr Darya, however, presented a far more complex and contentious challenge. For nearly a decade after the collapse of the Soviet Union, water management in the Syr Darya Basin was marked by uncoordinated and often chaotic usage by the newly independent states. It was not until 1998 that the riparian countries agreed to allocate water resources between upstream

hydropower production and downstream irrigation needs.⁸ This arrangement sought to balance the competing priorities of upstream Kyrgyzstan with downstream Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Kazakhstan.

Despite challenges in implementing this agreement, tensions never escalated into outright conflict. One key factor was an extended period of high precipitation during those years, which temporarily alleviated water scarcity. A more abundant “water pie” reduced the pressure on riparian states to compete over resources, enabling a relatively stable framework for managing the Syr Darya’s waters where its fragility is strongly linked to interannual variability of precipitation and the resulting amounts of runoff. This was demonstrated between 2007 and 2009 when a succession of dry years coincided with high crop and hydrocarbon prices on international markets and two major dam projects in the upstream countries (Kambarata in Kyrgyzstan and Rogun in Tajikistan). This led to a renewed debate with hostile rhetoric on how to allocate water resources in the transboundary river basin.

Relations amongst the riparian countries—which were turbulent, if not hostile, for the first 25 years of new nationhood—have improved considerably in recent years, especially after the new administration under President Mirziyoyev came into power in Uzbekistan in 2016. Downstream Uzbekistan is now even co-investing (together with Kyrgyzstan) in upstream dam projects in the large river cascades, something unthinkable a few years ago.

However, climate change is bound to test this collaboration. To better understand how climate change will interface with the historical water relations discussed above, we now look at climate impacts based on coupled climate-hydrological models. These models quantify changes in future water supplies based on projected temperature and precipitation forcings. They paint a complex picture of the region’s future hydrology.⁹ Figure 2 illustrates the projected relative hydrological changes in the Amu Darya and Syr Darya by the end of the 21st century under different climate scenarios. The Amu Darya basin shows a predominantly positive response, with water availability increases from approximately 4 percent (relative to current levels) under the most optimistic scenario to a more substantial 12 percent for a middle road scenario, followed by slightly lower increases in the higher emission scenarios. In contrast, the Syr Darya basin exhibits a more concerning trend, with minimal changes under lower emission scenarios but notable decreases in water availability, reaching about -7 percent under the highest emission scenario.

The differences in runoff patterns between the Amu Darya and Syr Darya can be partially explained by the vital role of glacier melt in stabilizing future water availability. The Amu Darya basin has extensive glaciation in its high-altitude regions, with glacier volumes nearly double those of the Syr Darya. Additionally, these glaciers are situated at much higher elevations, causing them to melt more slowly than the lower-elevation glaciers of the Syr Darya basin.

This means the Amu Darya will benefit from prolonged glacier melt well into the second half of the 21st century, acting as a critical buffer against declining water flows from other sources due to climate change. In contrast, with its smaller and lower-elevation glaciers, the Syr Darya is likely to experience a faster depletion of its ice reserves.

This contrast underscores that climate change is likely to have differing impacts on water resources in Central Asia, with significant implications for regional water management and adaptation strategies. Whether further climatic changes and increased water abstraction will tip the balance toward severe conflict or foster cooperation depends on the region’s ability to leverage these differences in hydrological trends.

Figure 2: Climate-scenario-dependent projected mean changes in water availability by the end of the 21st century. Values are in percentages relative to baseline values. The SSP scenarios from SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5 represent increasingly severe climate futures, ranging from sustainable development with strong mitigation (SSP1-2.6) through middle-of-the-road development (SSP2-4.5) and regional rivalry (SSP3-7.0) to fossil-fuel-driven growth with highest emissions (SSP5-8.5).¹⁰

The above historical and climate change analysis shows that we should, generally, be more worried about international water conflicts in the Syr Darya than in the Amu Darya catchment. What does this mean for the region's most acute current water management challenge, which concerns the Qosh Tepa Canal in the Amu Darya catchment?

The Qosh Tepa Canal

A new and arguably foreseeable challenge emanates from Afghanistan in the Amu Darya basin. In the country’s arid north, the new Qosh Tepa Canal, a government led project, promises to transform the nation’s agriculture. Designed to divert up to 20.5 billion cubic meters (bcm) of water annually from the Amu Darya River, the canal aims to irrigate 550,000 hectares of farmland, a bold step towards self-reliance and development.

Against the backdrop of increased climate stress, the Qosh Tepa Canal looms large. While Afghanistan has a legitimate claim to a reasonable and equitable share of the Amu Darya’s waters under general principles of international water law¹¹, the scale of the proposed diversion through the canal intensifies concerns about how water resources in the region are shared and managed in practice. Will the canal fulfill Afghanistan’s dreams of agricultural prosperity, or will it become a source of conflict with its neighbors? Can Central Asian countries adapt their

water-sharing arrangements to include Afghanistan, or will this project unravel years of cooperative water management?

To assess the potential impact of the Qosh Tepa Canal on Amu Darya’s water balance, it is useful to look at a representative development scenario. Presently, nearly 50 percent of the annual renewable water supply reaches the downstream (the region inside the black box in Figure 1, shared between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, including Karakalpakstan, Tashauz, and Horezm) under average climatic conditions, ensuring a relatively balanced distribution of water resources between upstream and downstream regions. Figure 3 shows the Amu Darya's current average main water balance components.

When the irrigation systems fed by the Qosh Tepa Canal are fully developed, typical irrigation requirements can be calculated based on a crop mix characteristic of Northern Afghanistan. This scenario would necessitate an estimated 10.3 bcm of irrigation water, which would be directly diverted from the Amu Darya. Figure 4 shows the river’s water balance under this scenario. Here, we consider increased irrigation requirements of +10 percent, on average, due to climate-induced general warming over the 21st century. While this upstream abstraction is partially offset by the anticipated long-term increase in water availability due to climate change, the net effect would still dramatically reduce water available to downstream territories in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan.

The Uzbek and Turkmen tail-end provinces along the Amu Darya mentioned above (Figure 1) depend exclusively on the Amu Darya for agriculture and other purposes and would bear the brunt of reduced water availability. Despite the mitigating influence of climate-induced changes in runoff, the scale of upstream diversion under this scenario and a general increase of irrigation water requirements due to the warming would significantly exacerbate water scarcity in these regions, intensifying the pressure on already vulnerable agricultural systems and livelihoods there. This underscores the urgent need for transboundary water management strategies that account for the interconnected impacts of infrastructure development and climate change, including the riparian states of the basin.

Figure 3: Mean current water balance of Amu Darya (data are averaged from 2010- 2022). Flows are in bold font and are in billions of cubic meters (bcm). The country-specific discharge contributions are as follows. KGZ: 2.3 bcm, TJK: 33.5 bcm, and AFG: 14.9 bcm. Source: Tobias Siegfried, hydrosolutions GmbH.

Figure 4: Projected mean end-of-century water balance of Amu Darya with Qosh Tapa irrigating 550'000 ha and under the most extreme climate scenario with slightly increased average discharge values (see Figure 2) and an estimated 10 percent increase in irrigation water demand relative to the baseline. Source: Tobias Siegfried, hydrosolutions GmbH.

Policy implications

For now, the most critical risk of international water conflict in Central Asia emanates from the Qosh Tapa Canal project. The ramifications of this project extend far beyond economic hardship by fundamentally altering the water dynamics of the Amu Darya Basin, and the canal risks destabilizing the fragile equilibrium of water management politics in Central Asia. As explained above, Afghanistan's exclusion from existing water-sharing agreements exposes a critical gap in regional governance, further complicating the situation. Moreover, the interplay between water resources and broader regional issues cannot be overlooked.

As construction of the Qosh Tapa Canal progresses, there is an urgent need to recalibrate water-sharing frameworks to include Afghanistan, to ensure sustainable and equitable resource distribution. This challenge is compounded by the pressures of climate change and population growth, but it also presents an opportunity. With the right strategies, the Canal could serve as a catalyst for renewed water diplomacy, fostering dialogue and collaboration among all riparian nations, and better preparing the region to face the threats posed by climate change. A preliminary agreement to this end between Uzbekistan and Afghanistan in early May 2025 indicates first steps in this direction.

State-of-the-art tools like hydrological modeling, hydro-economic tradeoff analysis, and space-based remote sensing can provide valuable insights to guide these negotiations. Moreover, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan need to invest heavily in the rehabilitation of the canal network. In many locations, more than 50 percent of the water resources allocated for irrigation are lost unproductively between the intake location and the field. Reducing these losses adds room for maneuver and ensures that the resources are allocated in an economically efficient and sustainable way. Due to the projected long-term drying in the Syr Darya River basin, the increase in water conveyance and application efficiency is all the more relevant there too.

Furthermore, leveraging issue linkages, such as energy dependencies, could build trust and incentivize transboundary cooperation beyond the water realm, demonstrating the value of

interdependence in the region's shared future. With international support and a commitment to facts-based decision-making, Central Asia can transform a looming water crisis into a framework for long-term stability in the water domain.

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